

A review on the possibility of using artificial intelligence to cure neurological and physiological disorders.

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Introduction

According to the facts and statistics presented by Alzheimer Disease International supported by the World Health Organization (WHO), worldwide, there were about 55 million people that lived with dementia in 2019. This number will just about double every 20 years, expected to reach around 78 million by the year 2030 and 139 million in 2050. This increase is mostly expected to take place in developing countries. Currently, 60% of people in dementia live in middle income countries, but by 2050, this will rise to 71%. The most rapid increase in the elderly population at the moment is taking place in China, India, and the south Asian and western Pacific region. Demographic aging is a worldwide process that is used to indicate the success of improved healthcare over the last century. More people are now living healthier and longer lives which results in the world population having a larger proportion of older people. Dementia mainly only affects the older population, though, there is a growing awareness of cases where people have had dementia before reaching the age of 65. There are over 10 million new cases of dementia each year worldwide, implying one

new case comes to the surface every 3.2 seconds.

Figure 1:- Growth in number of people with dementia

One of the most prominent neurological disorder is the Alzheimer's disease that causes the brain to atrophy (sink) and brain cells to die. It is the most common type of dementia — affecting a person's ability to function independently due to the continuous decline in thinking, behavioral and social skills. Amyloid beta protein ($A\beta$) along with Tau proteins plays a vital role in the cause of Alzheimer Disease.

Amyloid beta proteins represent peptides of around 36–43 amino acids which are the primary constituents of the amyloid plaques found in the brains of Alzheimer Disease patients. Amyloid precursor protein can also be represented by the abbreviation APP. It is

¹ "ADI - Dementia Statistics". *Alzint.Org*, 2022, <https://www.alzint.org/about/dementia-facts-figures/dementia-statistics/>. Accessed 22 Dec 2022.

an integral membrane protein that is present in numerous tissues, concentrated in the synapses of neurons.²

Tau protein is a microtubule-associated protein, predominantly expressed in the neurons, closely associated with the proper functioning of the cytoskeletal network in terms of microtubule assembly.³

It is already recognized that the disorderly protein buildup within the brain cells is what causes the disease. The type 1 membrane glycoprotein known as amyloid precursor protein (APP) is crucial for a number of biological processes, some of which are neuron development, signaling, intracellular transport, and other facets of neuronal homeostasis. The endoplasmic reticulum (ER) serves as the site of APP synthesis. From there, it is moved to the Golgi complex, where it matures completely before being moved to the plasma membrane. In order to produce A β , β -secretase and γ -secretase cleave mature APP at the plasma membrane in succession.

Human APP genes begin to mutate, which causes the A β protein to begin to build up in cells. The hallmarks of Alzheimer's disease appear to be the extra cellular buildup of A β in neurotic plaques and the binding of A β to a variety of receptors as a result of the accumulation of A β proteins in plaques

around brain cells. A β oligomers were postulated to produce mitochondrial malfunction and oxidative stress in neurons affected by Alzheimer's disease, leading to a huge calcium influx and neurotoxicity in neurons. The binding of A β to a number of receptors has been proposed as the origin of the neuronal toxicity. Neurons are damaged; they lose connections to each other and eventually die. Previously, studies pointed to A β fibrils being the neurotoxic agent that led to cellular death, memory loss, and other Alzheimer's Disease characteristics. Nonetheless, over the last two decades, further investigation has assisted with the suggestion that that oligomeric or prefibrillar species of the A β peptide are the most damaging to neuronal cells.

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Figure 2:- Magnification of plaques formation

Tau protein also contributes significantly to the development of Alzheimer's disease, along with A β protein. The fundamental job of the tau protein is to keep a neuron's internal support and transport system, which carries items like nutrition, around. Tau proteins, on the other hand, transform into formations

² Trambauer, J. et al. "Analyzing Amyloid-B Peptide Modulation Profiles And Binding Sites Of γ -Secretase Modulators". *Methods In Enzymology*, 2017, pp. 157-183. Elsevier, doi:10.1016/bs.mie.2016.10.013. Accessed 21 Dec 2022.

³ Garg, Ravindra Kumar et al. "Pathophysiology Of Acute Disseminated Encephalomyelitis". *Multiple Sclerosis*, 2016,

pp. 201-248. Elsevier, doi:10.1016/b978-0-12-800763-1.00010-5. Accessed 21 Dec 2022.

⁴ Rahman, M. Mahafuzur, and Christofer Lendel. "Extracellular Protein Components Of Amyloid Plaques And Their Roles In Alzheimer'S Disease Pathology". *Molecular Neurodegeneration*, vol 16, no. 1, 2021. Springer Science And Business Media LLC, doi:10.1186/s13024-021-00465-0. Accessed 22 Dec 2022.

known as neurofibrillary tangles as a result of the APP gene mutation. These tangles harm cells and cause the transport system to malfunction. As a result, it inhibits neural transmission and prevents neurons from passing through synapse.

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Figure 3:- Neurons arrangements in normal person and Alzheimer patient brain

Theory of intelligence

Intelligence is the ability to learn from experience, using metacognitive processes to enhance learning, and the capacity to adapt to the surrounding environment; it may require different adaptations within different social and cultural contexts.⁶

The theory of intelligence encompasses different ideas about what intelligence is and how it can be measured. There are several categories of theories, including

psychometric, cognitive, cognitive-contextual, and biological theories.

Psychometric Theories

Psychometrics is the branch of psychology concerned with testing, measuring, assessment, and associated activities. Psychometric theories are founded on the idea that intelligence is depicted as a combination of abilities measured by mental tests. For example, the results of a number-series test may reveal a weighted composite of the numbers in a difficult series, reasoning⁷, and memory⁸ abilities. Mathematical models allow a deficit in an area of test performance to be compensated by a great proficiency in the other. Superior thinking ability can compensate for a lack of numerical skill. There are several methods for testing IQ, and various scientists use different methods. The first is Charles E. Spearman who used the technique of "general factor," "It means that people who fared well on one mental-ability test were likely to perform well on others, whereas persons who did badly on the one were also likely to perform poorly on others . From this discovery, he came to the conclusion that intelligence is a general cognitive skill that researchers can quantify and describe statistically. Subsequently, L.L. Thurstone, an American psychologist, disagreed with Spearman's idea, saying that there were seven elements, which he referred to as "basic mental talents." As per Thurstone, such seven

⁵ "Amyloid Plaques And Neurofibrillary Tangles | Brightfocus Foundation". *Brightfocus.Org*, 2015, <https://www.brightfocus.org/news/amyloid-plaques-and-neurofibrillary-tangles>. Accessed 22 Dec 2022.

⁶ "APA Psycnet". *Psycnet.Apa.Org*, 2022, <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2017-32525-010>. Accessed 27 Dec 2022.

⁷ Reason. (2023). Retrieved 21 February 2023, from <https://www.britannica.com/topic/reason>

⁸ Memory | Definition, Retrieval, & Forgetting. (2023). Retrieved 21 February 2023, from <https://www.britannica.com/science/memory-psychology>

qualities were oral knowledge and understanding (as involved in vocabulary learning and reading), linguistic fluency (as involved in writing and generating phrases), amount (as needed to solve fairly simple mathematical expressions and arithmetical reasoning problems), spatial visualization (as involved in visualizing and attempting to manipulate objects, like fitting a set of suitcases into an automobile trunk), inductive reasoning (as engaged in inductive reasoning problems). Along with this, there were many additional beliefs on the different forms of intelligence that human minds possess, such as Fluid vs Crystallized Intelligence. As a result, both classic and current psychometric theories have flaws. First, it has yet to be demonstrated that a fully broad capacity spanning all mental talents exists. Second, psychometric theories cannot fully define all that goes on in the mind. Finally, it is not apparent if the tests on which psychometric theories are founded are equally relevant in all cultures.

Cognitive theories

In American research, Lee Cronbach's call to bring together psychologists who studied individual differences and those who studied commonalities in human behavior resulted in the development of cognitive theories of intelligence and of the underlying processes posited by these theories. Cognitive theories are those that relate to, are, or involve conscious intellectual activity such as thinking, reasoning, or remembering. The test interpreter can identify through cognitive analysis how much of the low score is due to weak reasoning skills and how much is due to a lack of word knowledge.

The underlying premise of the majority of cognitive approaches to intelligence is that intelligence consists of processes that may operate on mental representations of information (such as propositions or images). The test interpreter can identify through cognitive analysis how much of the low score is due to weak reasoning skills and how much is due to a lack of word knowledge. The underlying premise of the majority of cognitive approaches to intelligence is that intelligence consists of processes that may operate on mental representations of information (such as propositions or images). It is expected that a more intelligent person will express knowledge more concisely and will process it more quickly. Researchers have tried to gauge how quickly different types of thinking occur. They break down the total time needed to complete a task into the individual times needed to carry out each mental activity using mathematical modeling. The test interpreter can identify through cognitive analysis how much of the low score is due to weak reasoning skills and how much is due to a lack of word knowledge.

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As a result, computer modeling has not yet fully addressed several significant issues in comprehending the nature of intelligence. Michael E. Cole, a psychologist from the United States, for instance, has suggested that cognitive processing fails to account for the possibility that conceptions of intelligence differ between cultures and cultural groups. Yet, actual experience has shown that while traditional tests can predict academic success, they cannot anticipate how knowledge will be utilized.

Cognitive-contextual theories

Cognitive-contextual theories investigate how cognitive processes function in various situations. The ideas of Howard Gardner, an American psychologist, and Sternberg are two examples of this type. In 1983, Gardner presented the concept of "many intelligences," which challenged the premise of a single intelligence. Based on culturally valued qualities and abilities, he proposed eight distinct intelligences: verbal, logical-mathematical, geographical, artistic, physiological, interpersonal, and intrapersonal intelligence. Gardner's study on multiple intelligences led him to the conclusion that, whereas most ideas of

intelligence were culturally diverse and culturally biased, his was broad as it was predicated on biological and merge data, in addition to information generated from the mental function of a wide variety of individuals. Sternberg's "triarchic"⁹ hypothesis was an alternative method that took cognitive and cultural environment into consideration (1985). Sternberg posited three ("triarchic") linked and associated components of intelligence that, in that order, are involved with a person's inner world, surrounding world, and experience. The cognitive functions and concepts that provide the basis for all thought are covered in the first section. The second step is to apply these processes and representation to the outside world. The third aspect of intelligence is the synthesis of the internal and outside worlds via experience. This entails being able to apply previously learned information to new or entirely unrelated circumstances. In addition, John Mayer and Peter Salovey defined psychological intelligence as the capacity to recognize emotions, access and generate emotions to enhance cognition, interpret feelings and emotional knowledge, and comment on emotions to promote emotional and intellectual progress.

Biological Theories

Biological theories advocate a completely new approach that excludes mental ideas. Such supporters, known as reductionists, think that discovering intelligence's biological basis is the only way to truly

⁹ Ruhl], [Charlotte. "[Intelligence: Definition, Theories & Testing]". <https://www.simplypsychology.org/Intelligence.html>, 2020, p. ., <https://www.simplypsychology.org/intelligence.html#:~:text=>

According%20to%20the%20triarchic%20theory,problems%20and%20arrive%20at%20solutions. Accessed 24 Feb 2023.

appreciate it. Biological methods to intelligence should be considered as complementary to other methodologies, according to analogies that compare the human brain to a computer.

What is Intelligence Augmentation?

Augmented intelligence is a design pattern that emphasizes a partnership between humans and artificial intelligence (AI) to enhance cognitive performance. It focuses on building systems that augment and support human cognition, showcasing how AI and humans can complement each other and coexist in a mutually beneficial fashion. The idea behind IA is to amplify human potential by leveraging technology to surge work productivity, ease humdrum routine work, and enhance the overall quality of life.

The concept of IA seeks to demonstrate how humans and AI can collaborate to achieve better outcomes. The human is at the heart of the human-computer interaction, and IA technologies are designed to augment human decision-making and enhance human capabilities. Unlike AI, IA seeks to enable humans to make evidence-informed decisions while leveraging the power of algorithms to augment human performance.

Figure 4:- Intelligence Augmentation

IA technologies are used in different fields and can broadly be classified into four categories: enterprise, autonomous vehicles, robots/industrial IoT, and drones. For instance, Augmented Reality (AR) glasses, also known as smart glasses, are used in various industries such as oil, mining, healthcare, and automotive. They are wearable computer glasses that allow the wearer to see additional information alongside what they would usually see.

Another example is autonomous vehicles that enable automated driving on highways and within other access-controlled situations. However, humans are still needed to control the overall system and handle exceptions. IA technologies are not designed to replace humans, but rather to supplement and support their capabilities.

The spectrum of human-machine intelligence interaction ranges from assisted intelligence to augmented intelligence and autonomous intelligence. In assisted intelligence approaches, machines might undertake the action, but humans are making the decisions. In augmented intelligence methods, machines are taking actions and making decisions in collaboration with humans. In autonomous systems, machines are both

doing the actions and making the decisions without human intervention.¹⁰

In summary, IA is a model that emphasizes the partnership between humans and AI to enhance cognitive performance, including decision-making and learning. IA technologies are designed to augment human capabilities, not replace them. They are widely used in different fields and enable humans to achieve better outcomes. The human-machine intelligence interaction continuum ranges from assisted intelligence to augmented intelligence and autonomous intelligence, and each approach has its unique advantages and limitations.

According to Rold, one of the most well-known uses of AI in recent years has been thought-controlled prosthetic limbs. However, many of the commercially available AI-branded technologies ought to be classified as IA. These two strategies and another concept, aided intelligence, can all be placed on a scale. There is a continuum of interactions between human and machine intelligence that ranges from instances where machines are repeating many of the tasks humans are already doing (assisted), to situations where humans are being enhanced to do more than they are currently capable of doing (augmented), to situations where tasks are fully completed on their own without human intervention (autonomous). Machines may carry out the action in aided intelligence

approaches, but people still make the decisions. In approaches utilizing "augmented intelligence," machines take actions and make decisions alongside humans, or "collaborative human-machine decision making," but in "autonomous systems," machines carry out both the activities and the decision-making independently of human intervention. Organizations and people can perform things they couldn't otherwise do with the help of enhanced intelligence, autonomous intelligence systems act independently, and assisted intelligence enhances what people and organizations are currently doing.¹¹

In what ways would IA interact with humans?

IA is not a programming language or a code, but rather a system that is a distinct and developed kind of artificial intelligence. The system will integrate itself with many sorts of input devices (each crucial for a job) to provide outputs that people can better use and interpret. With the primary goal of creating a symbiotic interaction between humans and artificial intelligence, IA will usher in a revolutionary development in the field of medical sciences. According to a paper published in a journal regarding transactions of human-computer interaction¹², We may deduce that IA will be able to discover patterns in our daily lives, find abnormalities, save and analyze data, and process it, gradually adding value to our lives. The data

¹⁰ Hassani, H., Silva, E., Unger, S., TajMazinani, M., & Mac Feely, S. (2020). Artificial Intelligence (AI) or Intelligence Augmentation (IA): What Is the Future?. *AI*, 1(2), 143-155. doi: 10.3390/ai1020008

¹¹ Definition of Augmented Intelligence - Gartner Information Technology Glossary. (2023). Retrieved 24 February 2023, from

<https://www.gartner.com/en/information-technology/glossary/augmented-intelligence>

¹² "ACM TRANSACTIONS ON COMPUTER-HUMAN INTERACTION Home". *ACM Transactions On Computer-Human Interaction*, 2023, <https://dl.acm.org/journal/tochi>. Accessed 24 Feb 2023.

in this example can include talks that are broken down using artificial intelligence, attitudes that can be recognized using pitch and amplitude in human voice, environmental factors that can be discovered using sonar, and then advise the individual based on their disease. While all of the systems we discuss are now still theoretical, there is a strong potential that they will become a reality before the end of this decade. These will require a lot of new types of programming which will combine artificial intelligence and human input to make an ideal symbiote.

Let us look at few examples of different paradigms where we may leverage IA to our advantage. An ideal system based on IA principles would accomplish the following tasks:

Blindness: If the system is able to use SONAR to identify things like obstacles, targets, places to sit, keep things on, and objects that we can use, the blind person will easily be able to identify everything around them and work accordingly. It will make their lives much easier and effective. Also, the system will be able to help the blind person in his activities outside their home. It can help them cross the road, identify the traffic and also help them with the directions to their destinations. The user and the machines will constantly interact and it will use principles of IA to decode and encode the information given to it. Such patterns can either be pre-programmed or the system can be told to learn by itself according to the environment it is in. Not only does it create a perfect symbiotic relationship between humans and

machines, but also solves a major problem for people who are “new to their blindness” or even people who have been blind a long time.

Autism: If we were to look at it from a neurological standpoint, we can also talk about autism. In the autistic spectrum, people tend to experience the following symptoms

- Difficulty in social interactions
- Difficulty in communication
- Restricted interest in other people’s feelings
- Restricted emotions for the patient themselves.

While something like the autistic spectrum cannot be properly treated, we can always use an IA based system which will always be with the user. It will develop patterns in the thinking way and the expressed thought of the user and also track all the people they interact with. It will have a constant mic function so that it can identify human emotions using pitch and amplitude in voice, and also give the patient a better way to express their thoughts. This way, one can develop a personalized system for each user. While it may seem challenging at first but like any other AI, an IA system will only need to be programmed once and the system will carry out its functions constantly. The system can guide a person in a safe manner into a social interaction and help them better communicate with other people which would not only be beneficial to the user but also the people around them.

Surgery: According to a study posted in brain communications in 2020, IA is and will be widely used in neurological clinical

decision making processes. The main work will be to look at the patient's illness, decode the problems of the patient and potentially give us a possible cure for the illness. Also, IA will use statistical probability to determine whether surgery would be the best for patients. Also, there have been many such cases where multiple doctors such as an orthodontist who used the help of an artificially intelligent system to carry out their surgery. An article in the Harvard business review mentions that with the growing age, the AI is "joining forces" with humans and gives a graphical representation on how the performance has increased as humans worked more with machines. However, when we talk about IA, its aim is not to "overthrow" humans, but to create a better working symbiotic relationship with humans. Doctors can combine their experience with the subject specific and in-depth knowledge of an IA system to produce the best of the surgery. For example, An Ideal IA system should be able to identify the differences between scans and reports of a healthy and unhealthy body, provide solutions to work further on this to the doctor, and help the doctor perform their medical procedures with high precision.

Depression: Even if we look at it from a neuropsychological perspective, we can create a different type of IA system which can be prescribed by psychiatrists. We can begin by allowing the system to help cheer up the user and put him in a better place according to his condition and requirements and talk to them to motivate them and make them a better version of themselves throughout the day and send a written update to his doctor in

every equal intervals of time. Also, it would make sure that the person completes the tasks he assigned himself and stays in a good and hygienic way by using its camera, motion tracking and AI skills to analyze images taken. It can even talk to the person if the "damage" can be solved on a minimal level. Also, it will use the microphone and the camera to track mood and emotional levels of the person constantly and report to the psychiatrist under severe conditions. If the user indulges in self harm, the authorities will be notified immediately.

How could IA help with Alzheimer's?

There are several ways in which AI can help detect symptoms of Alzheimer's or provide assistance and support while a person is suffering.

1. Using the CIPHERGEN's Seldi™ system

The primary causes of Alzheimer's has been confirmed to be amyloid beta proteins. Its deposition is the root of neurodegeneration, according to two primary lines of evidence. First, Ab 1-42, the longest and most deadly version, is produced more frequently as a result of mutations discovered in three genes in familial Alzheimer's patients. Second, cultured neuronal cells are poisoned by aggregated Ab. Thus, protease inhibitors that prevent the release of amyloid from the amyloid precursor protein are important therapeutic targets. Both aspartyl proteases, which are built into the membranes of the endoplasmic reticulum and Golgi network, are the ideal candidates for the releasing proteases. In order to assess all the Ab

variations in culture supernatants, a sensitive assay has been created using CIPHERGEN's Seldi™ system. This assay will be extremely helpful when screening inhibitors of these proteases. (Using biological samples directly, without the requirement for pre-analytical extractions or sample preparation, a CIPHERGEN's Seldi™ system is utilised to quickly perform the separation, detection, and analysis of proteins at the femtomole levels.) It has been demonstrated using this test that raising intracellular cholesterol boosts the activity of both γ -secretase-42 and b-secretase.

Figure 5:- CIPHERGEN's Seldi™ system

The specifics of the experiment, the arrays' quality, and the methods for analysis all affect how accurately SELDI ProteinChip arrays can measure the generation of Alzheimer's beta-amyloid in transfected cells. SELDI protein arrays, however, have generally been proved to be an effective method for tracking alterations in protein expression levels, including beta-amyloid. It is crucial to remember that the correctness and dependability of the results from SELDI

protein arrays should be confirmed using additional methods.¹³

Beta-amyloid, a protein that is a defining characteristic of Alzheimer's disease, can be detected using SELDI protein arrays. However, it is unclear that SELDI arrays can be used to detect Alzheimer's disease in its early stages because the condition is characterized by complex alterations in the brain that cannot be exclusively identified by changes in a single protein. Nevertheless, SELDI arrays are not yet widely accepted or validated as a diagnostic tool for Alzheimer's disease, and more studies are required to determine their clinical value. For an accurate Alzheimer's disease diagnosis and treatment, speak with a licensed healthcare professional.¹⁴

2. Using AI to provide assistance to caregivers that are taking care of people with Alzheimer's

Language impairment can also appear in the early stages of AD, despite the fact that memory loss is frequently thought of as the disease's signature symptom. Many predicted values, such as: 1) ease of speech recordings and follow-up over time, 2) non-invasiveness, and 3) improved speech analysis technology during the last decade, expanded by progress in artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning, determine the development in the use of speech as a diagnostic aspect for AD. The use of speech and language data obtained using a variety of

¹³ Brian M Austen; Emma R Frears; Huw Davies (2000). The use of Seldi ProteinChip™ Arrays to monitor production of Alzheimer's β -amyloid in transfected cells. , 6(9), 459–469. doi:10.1002/1099-1387(200009)6:9<459::aid-psc286>3.0.co;2-b

¹⁴MS, C. (2023). CIPHERGEN ProteinChip SELDI-TOF MS - Mckinley Scientific. Retrieved 2 April 2023, from <https://www.mckscientific.com/product/ciphergen-proteinchip-seldi-tof-ms/#:~:text=It%20is%20used%20to%20rap>

techniques together with computer voice processing have been used in recent works on AI in AD research for diagnosis, prognosis, or progression modeling. In the field of artificial intelligence known as "machine learning," prediction models are "learned" directly from data, and students improve their own effectiveness by "practicing" on more data. Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning-based research into automated language and speech interpretation has produced encouraging findings and attracted increasing attention.

An algorithm was trained to identify Alzheimer's patients by detecting glucose levels in the brain. Researchers have used images from the ADNI, a sizable public dataset of PET test results for people who were ultimately diagnosed with Alzheimer's disease or with mild to no cognitive issues, in the algorithm training. Gradually, the algorithm itself began to understand which traits are critical for forecasting and which are irrelevant for Alzheimer's disease diagnosis. The scientists tested the algorithm on two fresh datasets after it had been trained on 1,921 photos to see how well it performed. The initial set of images was made up of 188 images that came from the same ADNI database but hadn't yet been processed by the algorithm. According to the researchers, the second trial included a completely new set of scans collected from 40 people who had visited the UCSF Memory and Aging Center with signs of potential cognitive impairment.

Throughout the test, the algorithm performed flawlessly. In the first test set, 92% of people who developed Alzheimer's disease received a correct diagnosis, and in the second test set, 98% did. Furthermore, it accurately foresaw the patient's final diagnosis 75.8 months in advance, or a little over six years. The algorithm will next be evaluated and recalibrated using larger, more diversified information gathered from other hospitals and countries throughout the world, according to researchers. After passing these tests, researchers think the algorithm might be used by neuroscientists to forecast Alzheimer's disease when they visit a patient in a healthcare facility, enabling patients to receive treatment sooner rather than later.¹⁵

3. AI detecting whether a person has alzheimer's by observing and examining their face complexion

A study was conducted, which was aimed at examining whether artificial intelligence (AI) could distinguish between the faces of people with cognitive impairment and those without dementia. 121 patients with cognitive impairment and 117 cognitively sound participants were recruited for the study. 5 deep learning models with 2 optimizers were tested.¹⁶ The study showed that deep learning programs such as Xception have the ability to differentiate the faces of patients with mild dementia from that of patients without dementia, paving the way for future studies into the development of a facial biomarker

¹⁵ Mohammed, I. (2019). Artificial Intelligence for Caregivers of Persons with Alzheimer's Disease and Related Dementias: Systematic Literature Review. JETIR, 6(1), 741-744-741-744. Retrieved from <https://www.jetir.org/view?paper=JETIR1901E97>

¹⁶ Umeda-Kameyama, Yumi et al. "Screening Of Alzheimer'S Disease By Facial Complexion Using Artificial Intelligence". Aging, vol 13, no. 2, 2021, pp. 1765-1772. Impact Journals, LLC, doi:10.18632/aging.202545. Accessed 24 Feb 2023.

for dementia. However, this is a relatively new field, hence, a lot more research and exploration is required to make any definite conclusions.

Biological limitations

Alzheimer's disease is a complicated disease that affects people differently, either through a deterioration in cognitive or physical function. Several variables can limit Alzheimer's patients' capacity to participate in investigations and produce valid data samples. The loss in cognitive performance that is a characteristic of Alzheimer's disease is one of the fundamental biological limits. Patients may struggle to grasp instructions, finish activities, or give correct data as a result of this. Moreover, patients may struggle with memory, attention, and communication, limiting their capacity to engage in investigations.

Moreover, Alzheimer's disease impacts individuals differently, with distinct symptoms and progression rates. Because of this diversity, comparing results between individuals or generalizing findings to the larger community can be difficult. Some individuals, for example, might suffer from more severe memory loss than others, while others may have more apparent movement issues. This heterogeneity might hamper AI algorithms' capacity to reliably recognize patterns or make predictions.¹⁷ Aside from that, there may be a scarcity of data on

Alzheimer's patients, particularly in the initial stages of the illness, making it difficult to train AI models properly. Furthermore, the data acquired from Alzheimer's patients may be of low quality because of restrictions in imaging technologies or the disease's impact on cognitive and physical performance. Coupled with this, there are ethical considerations about employing AI in Alzheimer's research, such as privacy and informed permission. Patients, for example, may be apprehensive about their personal information being used or shared without their consent, or they may be unaware of the dangers and advantages of participating in research. Finally, there may be technical constraints to employing AI in Alzheimer's research, such as restricted access to specialist equipment or restrictions in the accuracy or dependability of the AI models. Certain imaging methods, for example, may be unable to identify abnormalities in the brain associated with Alzheimer's disease, or the models may be unable to distinguish Alzheimer's disease from other illnesses that influence cognitive performance.¹⁸

Therefore, while artificial intelligence has the potential to provide substantial insights into the biology of Alzheimer's disease, there are various biological limits that must be considered while doing studies on Alzheimer's patients. These constraints can have an impact on the quality, reliability, and generalizability of the results, and they must

¹⁷ Fabrizio, Carlo et al. "Artificial Intelligence For Alzheimer'S Disease: Promise Or Challenge?". *Diagnostics*, vol 11, no. 8, 2021, p. 1473. MDPI AG, doi:10.3390/diagnostics11081473. Accessed 4 Feb 2023.

¹⁸ de la Fuente Garcia, Sofia et al. "Artificial Intelligence, Speech, And Language Processing Approaches To

Monitoring Alzheimer'S Disease: A Systematic Review". *Journal Of Alzheimer's Disease*, vol 78, no. 4, 2020, pp. 1547-1574. IOS Press, doi:10.3233/jad-200888. Accessed 4 Feb 2023.

be carefully reviewed and addressed to ensure that the experiments are carried out in an ethical and effective manner.

Computational Limitations

When employing AI to conduct research on Alzheimer's patients, computational restrictions pose a substantial problem. While AI has the potential to provide significant insights into the biology of Alzheimer's disease, there are several computational limitations that must be considered when conducting experiments, such as the quality of data collected from Alzheimer's patients, which can be poor due to limitations in imaging technology or the disease's effects on cognitive and physical function. This makes it harder for AI programs to spot trends and make predictions. Also, there may be a scarcity of data on Alzheimer's patients, particularly in the early stages of the disease, making it difficult to train AI models efficiently. Moreover, data acquired from Alzheimer's patients may be skewed, for example, due to underrepresentation of specific demographic groups, limiting the generalizability of the findings. This bias can also have an impact on the accuracy and predictability of AI algorithms. Apart from that, AI models employed in trials on Alzheimer's patients may be exceedingly complicated, making it difficult to comprehend the data or understand how the models generate predictions. This can restrict scientists' and doctors' ability to utilize the findings to influence future research or treatment decisions. Experiments on Alzheimer's patients utilizing AI may necessitate large computational resources, such as high-performance computer systems,

which may not be available in all contexts. This may limit the availability of AI for studies in some places or for certain researchers. Moreover, certain AI models may be uninterpretable, which means it is difficult to comprehend how the models make predictions, limiting the value of the data for scientific or therapeutic applications. This can also make validating the results and understanding how the AI models might be improved in the future difficult. Furthermore, there may be a shortage of validation data accessible to corroborate the correctness of the AI models, making evaluation of their performance and dependability problematic. This can reduce scientists' and doctors' trust in the data and impair their ability to draw significant scientific or therapeutic conclusions.

Thus, while AI has the potential to provide important insights into the biology of Alzheimer's disease, various computational constraints must be considered while performing studies. These constraints can have an impact on the quality, reliability, and generalizability of the results and must be carefully reviewed and addressed to ensure that the experiments are carried out properly and efficiently.

Future Scope

Some of the prospective applications of AI in Alzheimer's therapy include: AI can identify a person's likelihood of acquiring Alzheimer's disease and give individualized treatment regimens based on genetics, lifestyle, and medical history. Moreover, artificial intelligence (AI) may be trained to evaluate brain scans and other medical

imaging to detect Alzheimer's disease in its earliest stages, allowing for earlier treatment and better outcomes. Aside from that, AI may aid in the discovery of novel treatments and cures by evaluating massive quantities of data and predicting how certain substances would affect the brain. In addition, AI may be utilized to create intelligent caregiving systems that can assist family members and carers in understanding the requirements and behavior of Alzheimer's patients and providing appropriate assistance. Additionally, AI can help researchers discover patients who would be ideal candidates for the experiment and analyze outcomes to assess the success of the treatment during the design and execution of clinical trials. AI can be used to track the evolution of Alzheimer's disease and give individualized therapies to assist patients control symptoms and enhance their quality of life. Finally, AI may be used to forecast future occurrences, such as cognitive function decrease, allowing for early intervention and improved outcomes.

Conclusion

Finally, AI has the potential to change Alzheimer's disease therapy. AI can assist improve the lives of individuals impacted by this horrible condition, from early diagnosis to individualized medication. Yet, it is critical to proceed with caution when it comes to AI in healthcare because the technology is still in its infancy and has yet to

be thoroughly validated in real-world contexts.

When it comes to screening for protein inhibitors, the Seldi Protector chip has a promising future. Further research is needed before it can be completely functional and attain its full potential. Yet, in order for AI to be beneficial in the treatment of Alzheimer's, rigorous scientific investigations and clinical trials must be conducted. Additionally, ethical and legal factors must be considered to guarantee that the technology is utilized responsibly and in a manner that safeguards patients' privacy and rights.

While there is still more work to be done, the future of AI in Alzheimer's therapy looks promising. AI has the potential to substantially enhance the lives of persons affected by Alzheimer's disease and give hope for a cure in the future with the correct investments in research and development and careful consideration of ethical and legal issues.

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